

Prevention of Cooperative E Black Hole Attacks and Emerging efficient in MANETs

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Abstract

Mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs) are extensively used in military and civilian applications. The dynamic topology of MANETs allows nodes to join and leave the networks at any point in time. The generic characteristic of MANET has rendered it vulnerable to security attacks. In this paper, we address the problem of coordinated attack by multiple black holes acting a group. We present a technique to identify several black holes cooperating with each other and a solution to discover a safe route avoiding cooperative black hole attack.

Keywords: ad hoc networks, black hole, security, routing, AODV

Introduction

Ad hoc networks have a large number of potential applications. Military uses such as connecting soldiers or other military units to each other on the battlefield or creating sensory arrays with thousands of sensors are two typical examples. Ad hoc networks provide a possibility of creating a network in situations where creating the infrastructure would be impossible or prohibitively expensive. Unlike a network with fixed the transportation, mobile nodes in ad hoc networks do not communicate via access points (fixed structures). Each mobile node acts as a host when requesting/providing information from/to other nodes in the network, and act as the router when discovering and maintaining routes for other nodes in the networks.

Each device in a MANET is free to move independently in any direction, and will, therefore, change its links to other devices frequently. Each must forward traffic unrelated to its own use, and hence be a router. The primary challenge in building a MANET is equipping each device to continuously maintain the information required to well route traffic. Such networks may operate by themselves or may be connected to the larger Internet. They may contain one or multiple and different transceivers between nodes. This results in a highly dynamic, autonomous topology.

Cooperative Black Hole Attack Problem Black Hole

A black hole has two properties. First, the node exploits the ad hoc

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routing protocol, such as AODV, to advertise itself as having a valid route to a destination node, even though the route is spurious, with the intention of intercepting packets. Second, the node consumes the intercepted packets. The following conventions for protocol representation.

Cooperative Black Hole Attack

According to the original AODV protocol, when source node S wants to communicate with the destination node D, the source node S broadcasts the route request (RREQ) packet. The neighboring active nodes update their routing table with an entry for the source node S, and check if it is the destination node or has a fresh enough route to the destination node. If not, the

Intermediate node updates the RREQ (increasing the hop count) and floods the network with the RREQ to the destination node D until it reaches node D or any other intermediate node which has a fresh enough route to D. The destination node D or the intermediate node with a new enough route to D, initiates a route response (RREP) in the reverse direction. Node S starts sending data packets to the neighboring node which responded first and discards the other responses. This works fine when the network has no malicious nodes.

Solution

In this section, we propose a methodology for identifying multiple black hole nodes cooperating as a group with a slightly modified AODV protocol by introducing Data Routing Information (DRI) Table and Cross Checking.

Data Routing Information Table

A routing table does not contain a list of all possible destinations. Rather, it contains a list of destinations that are next in line to the router. Each router contains this list, and when it receives packets of data it directs that packet to the next link or hop in the network until it reaches its final destination. Typically the routing table contains a list of IP addresses, Gateway addresses, and other information. Below, is an example of a very vital routing table.

Network Destination	Netmask	Gateway	Interface	Metric
0.0.0.0	0.0.0.0	192.168.0.1	192.168.0.100	10
127.0.0.0	255.0.0.0	127.0.1.1	127.0.1.1	5
192.168.0.0	255.255.255.0	192.168.0.100	192.168.0.100	10
192.168.5.100	255.255.255.255	127.0.5.1	127.0.5.1	20
192.168.55.255	255.255.255.255	192.168.3.100	192.168.3.100	15

Advantages of MANET

The obvious appeal of MANETs is that the network is decentralized and nodes/devices are mobile, that is to say, there is no fixed infrastructure which provides the possibility for numerous applications in different areas such as environmental monitoring disaster relief and military communications. Since the early 2000s interest in MANETs has significantly increased which, in part, is due to the fact mobility can improve network capacity, shown by Grossglauser and Tse along with the introduction of new technologies. One main advantage of a decentralized network is that they are typically more robust than centralized networks due to the multi-hop fashion in which information is relayed. For example, in the cellular network setting, a drop in coverage occurs if a base station stops working however, the chance of a single point of failure in a MANET are reduced significantly since the data can take

multiple paths. Since the MANET architecture evolves with time, it has the potential to resolve issues such as isolation/disconnection from the network. Further advantages of MANETS over networks with a fixed topology include flexibility (an ad hoc network can be created anywhere with mobile devices), scalability (you can simply add more nodes to the network) and lower administration costs (no need to build an infrastructure first).

With these positives follow some obvious drawbacks in network performance. With a time-evolving network it is clear we should expect variations in network performance due to no fixed architecture (no fixed connections). Furthermore, since network topology determines interference and thus connectivity, the mobility pattern of devices within the network will impact on network performance, possibly resulting in data having to be resent a lot of times (increased delay) and finally allocation of network resources such as power remains unclear. Finally, finding a model that accurately represents human mobility while enduring mathematically tractable remains an open problem due to the large range of factors that influence it. Some typical models used include the random walk, random waypoint and levy flight models.

Conclusion and Future Work

In this paper we have studied the routing security issues of MANETs, described the cooperative black hole attack that can be mounted against a MANET and proposed a feasible solution for it in the AODV protocol. The proposed solution can be applied by 1.) Identify multiple black hole nodes cooperating with each other in a MANET, and 2.) Discover secure paths from source to destination by avoiding various black hole nodes acting in cooperation. As future work, we intend to develop simulations to analyze the performance of the proposed solution. We also plan to study the impact of GRAY hole nodes (nodes which switch from good nodes to black hole nodes) and techniques for their identification.

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